

A Multi-level Linguistic Analysis of Chinese English: Interlanguage Features and

Abstract

This study investigates the linguistic variations of English spoken by native Chinese speakers, focusing on the systemic deviations from Standard English (SE). Based on an analysis of the 2014 podcast Chinglish Sweet Talk, the research examines phenomena across phonological, morphological, lexical, and syntactic levels.

Keywords: Chinglish, Interlanguage, Second Language Acquisition, L1 Interference, China English

Variational Patterns

The following text is an analysis of variation in English spoken in China by native Chinese speakers, and its deviation from standard forms of English. The analysis addresses the main language frameworks – phonology, morphology, lexis, syntax and discourse. The analysis is based on a source text provided in Appendix A.

1.0 Introduction

Chinglish is an interlanguage with a blend of Chinese syntax and grammar and English expressions. Owing to the significant differences between the two languages, Chinglish displays many features that are not present in standard English.

2.0 Phonological Analysis

One of the key aspects to analyze Chinglish is the phonological branch, focused on articulation patterns. As it can be referred from the first paragraph, an interviewer pronounces the word “see” as /seɪ/, which is not considered standard English pronunciation. This phenomenon can be explained by the contrasting phonological structures of the languages—while English relies on the vowels’ length distinction, hence, open and closed sounds, Chinese is known for its tonal system. For Chinese speakers, this prolonged duration of a vowel may be unfamiliar and therefore is substituted by the closest familiar sound within the Chinese phonological system, which would be /eɪ/.

In addition, throughout the text various omissions of consonants can be observed. For instance: “currently” - /kʌrɪnli:/, “always” - /ɔ:weɪs/, “called” - /kɒl/, “smart” - /smɑ:/:, “out” - /aʊ/. Once again, this can be attributed to the distinction between English and Chinese languages, particularly the fact that a lot of words in Chinese end with vowels, unlike in English, where words end with consonants. As a result, Chinese people might find such words hard to pronounce, causing consonant deletion.

Another detail worth mentioning is the enunciation of words “thousand” - /saʊsɔ:nd/ and “think” - /sɪnk/. These linguistic units are classic examples of the phoneme /θ/, which is a dental fricative. The Chinese language mostly has alveolar fricatives, such as /s/, rather than dental ones, which leads to challenges when trying to pronounce words with “th”. Therefore, the closest equivalent sound for Chinese speakers to use is /s/.

3.0 Morphological and Lexical Variability

Moving to the next linguistic characteristic of Chinglish, which centers on morphemes, particular conclusions can be drawn regarding Chinese structure as a language and its difference from the English one. For example, in Chinese plurals are expressed through measure words and numbers, consequently there is no change and no morphological variation of characters themselves, as they can act as independent units. Accordingly, Chinese often neglect plural endings when speaking English, as portrayed in the text: "how many foreigner(s)". This reflects a reliance on communicative redundancy where the numeral already provides the plural meaning.

Furthermore, since Chinese and English morphemes are dissimilar, mistakes are inevitable. The phrase "I'm very interesting", which should be "I'm very interested", occurs due to direct translation from Chinese to English. Mandarin does not distinguish -ed adjectives between -ing adjectives; characters in Chinese do not change form to express different concepts of "feeling interested" and "being interesting". Moreover, "I'm very interested" has a passive meaning and passive construction in Chinese forms dissimilarly, resulting in wrongly structured clauses and incorrect endings.

In terms of lexical items and their combination to form a specific language, one can notice cultural influences, especially American influence, and detect the informal register. Velvet uses expressions "chilling out", "pretty cool", "kinda", that are a major part of modern English and are used to create a natural flow in spoken speech. The presence of neologisms and blending of words, such as "Chinglish" and "webzine," allows creativity in English and brings new perspective and meaning to the word.

4.0 Syntactic Analysis

The syntactic field is, as one might say, the most remarkable because Chinese syntax is completely unlike that of English. First of all, in Chinese there is no inflected form of verbs according to the tense. Chinese natives use adverbs of time to tell if something happened in the past or is happening right now, or add the particle “了”. For this reason, Chinese learners may struggle with tenses and their usage in the narrative, as in “I always imagine”. The sentence "commercial going to coming to us" is an example of an incorrect frame of a sentence, containing the structure "be going to".

This also applies to auxiliary verbs. Despite Chinese having auxiliary verbs, they do not form tenses in a way that resembles English syntax. This is why learners may drop auxiliaries and fail to use them properly: "(do) you have anything to say on this", "(do) you think", "how many foreigners (are) in Shanghai", “company’s commercials (are) going to”. This can emphasize the informal tone of the conversation as well.

Besides, Chinese learners have no frame of reference in Chinese for English prepositions, hence, they tend to make analogies of what they have learnt and apply them in new situations: "the focus is in Beijing", "working in Shanghai (at) some point", "at the top ten". Along with prepositions, Chinese does not have articles, instead it uses classifiers. The lack of an equivalent article system in Chinese leads to omissions and mistakes: "a English webzine", "a English site", "I'm not like (a) technical guy".

Additionally, in Mandarin the absence of a subject in the sentence is normal and, in most cases, grammatically correct and understandable, since the topic is largely derived from the context. However, English is less flexible in this aspect, and for English speakers, the elimination of the main subject can be confusing, as in: "I think (it) is not".

5.0 Discourse and Conclusion

Apart from the characteristics reviewed above, discourse, too, offers an insight into formality differences and cohesive devices. Understanding these errors also helps the translator choose more adequate equivalents and avoid calques.

The text contains discourse markers, such as “like”, “okay so”, “you know”, contributing to changing the topic. Expressions “long time no see” and “he was like” highlight the casual discussion between speakers.

In conclusion, Chinglish, which is a variety of English heavily influenced by Chinese language structure, deviates from standard English on several linguistic levels.

6.0 Bibliography

Interviewer, I., & Tiny, T. (Hosts). (2014). Chinglish Sweet Talk [Audio podcast episode].

Selinker, L. (1972). Interlanguage. *International Review of Applied Linguistics in Language Teaching*, 10(1-4), 209-232.

Chinglish - Wikipedia, дата последнего обращения: марта 7, 2026,

Appendix A.

Text A – edited excerpts from a podcast called Chinglish Sweet Talk, posted online in 2014. The three speakers are Chinese. Two of them are interviewers. The other speaker, the interviewee, has a job working on an English online magazine in China.

I: Interviewer

T: Tiny (second interviewer)

V: Velvet (guest)

Podcast introduction

I: hello everyone (.) and here is our (.) third episode of the Chinglish Sweet Talk and (.) long time no see /sei/ how are you (.) and today we actually have a very special guest

V: hello everyone er my name is Velvet I'm currently /kʌŋʌnli:/ in Beijing right now and (.) I work for a English webzine kind of lifestyle website (2)

I: ok cool

V: it's called /kɒl/ er smart /sma:/ Shanghai dot com and smart Beijing dot com and I'm I'm right now sort of more on the Beijing site and I do a little bit Shanghai (.) social media but (.) I'm in Beijing and I (.) just (.) the focus is in Beijing

I: so how is the experience

V: it was fun to work for them and yeah it was er pretty cool and I think is not (.) the same as other er kinda er top five hundred company kind of job but you know we we I'm not like (.) sort of office

lady whatever that kind of stuff I'm like just chilling out /ɑʊ/ and the job is quite cool and quite not mainstream let's just say that

When discussing the success of the online magazine

I: like (.) say (.) if er like hundreds of them (.) like (.) English sites are (.) opening in China (.) so you think Smart Shanghai would be at the top ten

V: yes I'm sure about that it's it's all about the traffic we've I think they've studied not me I'm not like technical guy I've just heard that you know from my boss that he's so confident and he was like yeah we are definitely number one we have like all this traffic and I I think that's why he's always /ɔ:weɪs/ been telling me that of all the er company's commercials going to coming to us (.) not (.) we going for them

I: ok so (.) talking about traffic (.) so (.) Tiny actually has his own site called Our Coders you have anything to say on this

T: er I don't know how to compare a Chinese site and a English site but I really have a question do you know how many foreigner in Shanghai

V: erm (.) I'm not sure how many foreigners are in Shanghai

T: yes (.) er I think /sɪŋk/ as a tourist (.) and as er (.) working in Shanghai some point (.) do you have the number

I: um things I've heard I think it's something around er two hundred thousand people

T: two hundred thousand /saʊsɔ:nd/ ok so er I'm very interesting about the website because I always imagine if I am a foreigner I go to Shanghai how to er how to how to get the information so the first question is how how do I know this website